

Using a data dictionary to enrich the IFC schema

This article is aimed at information management professionals dealing with structured data in the construction industry.

A bit of background

You may have heard about the free service provided by the buildingSMART International called bSDD. bSDD is a comprehensive library of data dictionaries – classes, properties, relations, restrictions, units, etc.; it offers a structured and standardized approach to data classification. Its API-first design enables seamless integration with software tools, making it an ideal platform for enriching the IFC schema.

RECONMATIC team proposed to utilise bSDD to publish a set of properties to deal with properties that could enhance component and material reusability and recycling. As part of the discovery phase, we stumbled upon brilliant research by Arghavan Akbarieh, who accomplished her Ph.D. at the University of Luxembourg and currently carries her work at the Eindhoven University of Technology. Her deep research on Decommissioning and Reuse is captured in her dissertation ‘Information Modelling For Circular Transformation Of Built Assets’ End-Of-Life’.

BIMBox collaborated with Arghavan to translate the Decommissioning and Reuse (DOR) ontology ([Ontology Documentation generated by WIDOCO \(z-arghavan.github.io\)](#)) into a practical set of properties that can be utilised by industry professionals using the bSDD.

If you want to explore DOR follow this link: [Decommissioning and Reuse 0.0.1 \(bSDD\) \(buildingsmart.org\)](#)

When shall I use the data dictionary?

If you are considering utilising the data dictionary, it is probably because you couldn't find properties already defined in the IFC schema. If that's the case, chances are that the properties you need have already been defined by someone else and are free to access through bSDD. Just check the list of organizations and their published data dictionaries here: [buildingSMART Data Dictionary Search \(bSDD\)](#) before you go to the next step.

If you still find yourself in a position where the properties you want to define are not there, you can propose your definitions.

Where do you start?

First of all, you will need to read a bit of documentation. We know it's not exciting, but there is no way around it. Luckily, bSDD team has a great resource on GitHub: [bSDD/Documentation at master · buildingSMART/bSDD · GitHub](#)

Once you open the documentation, it might seem overwhelming as it is rather technical. However, if you're not a software developer but a mere mortal who wants to enrich IFC (or anything else) you'll need two major components:

- Register your organisation on bSDD by filling an online form here [Request new organisation to be added to bSDD - buildingSMART User Helpdesk - Jira Service Management \(atlassian.net\)](#), and
- Utilise json or Excel template to record your properties and classes.

Since we are not so versatile in using json we opted for an Excel template. First of all, download the latest bSDD template from GitHub. You can access it here: [bSDD/Model/Import Model/spreadsheet-import at master · buildingSMART/bSDD · GitHub](https://github.com/buildingSMART/bSDD/blob/master/Model/Import%20Model/spreadsheet-import%20at%20master)

Once you have the template, you'll need to follow stringent rules defined here: [bSDD/Documentation/bSDD JSON import model.md at master · buildingSMART/bSDD · GitHub](https://github.com/buildingSMART/bSDD/blob/master/Documentation/bSDD%20JSON%20import%20model.md). The template also has valuable tips to assist the user. By utilising the template, you will be able to not only define your properties, classes and materials, but also link them to existing definitions found in bSDD. It is actually best practice to link property definitions to existing classes or other domain properties, including IFC, to save time and preserve consistency. The documentation is brilliant and relatively easy to follow, with accommodating graphics, tips and examples.

Where do you finish?

Once you have your definitions ready, it is time to test the upload. First, read the import tutorial: [bSDD/Documentation/bSDD import tutorial.md at master · buildingSMART/bSDD · GitHub](https://github.com/buildingSMART/bSDD/blob/master/Documentation/bSDD%20import%20tutorial.md). If you used the Excel template like us, you must convert it to json. To do so, there is another brilliant tutorial and converter provided by the bSDD team. Follow the link [bSDD/Model/Import Model/spreadsheet-import at master · buildingSMART/bSDD · GitHub](https://github.com/buildingSMART/bSDD/blob/master/Model/Import%20Model/spreadsheet-import%20at%20master) to access the Python converter. At this stage, it might get a bit technical; however, try following the steps described, and if you stumble on some technical issues, ChatGPT can help.

If you got everything right and converted an Excel file into json it is time to upload it onto the bSDD management site. If there are any issues in your json file, the prompts given upon the upload are great tips for correcting the file.

Finally, if you cleared all the warnings, you will see your data definitions on the bSDD site. The first upload is in 'Preview' mode in case you want to adjust your dictionary, but once you are ready, you can activate your content so you and others can utilise it in their preferred software.

Good luck!

By the way, it may seem that we have figured this out all by ourselves, yet this explainer would not have been possible without exemplary guidance and support from Artur Tomczak!

